

D1.21

Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: University of
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D1.21 REPORT ON SUSTAINABILITY OF THE ONE HEALTH EJP WEBSITE

Background Information

The One Health EJP website underwent major redevelopment/redesign work to enhance/refresh its stability, security, and functionality, and improve the user experience. This work was outsourced to the external website development company, Barclay Works, which was overseen by the Director, Gary Barclay. The company had already been providing professional website services for annual administration, maintenance work and technical support of the One Health EJP website since 2021, hence being a trusted service provider. These existing services included platform updates, third party plugin updates, remote-offsite daily backups, monthly backup recovery testing (with backups available to client), S3 Amazon storage, site monitored hourly for malicious activity, *ad-hoc* maintenance, and change requests and provisioning on ticket tracking support system. The redevelopment work was started in July 2022 and was completed in September 2023 by Barclay Works. Some delays in completion of the work occurred due to some unexpected issues that arose and unforeseen personal circumstances.

1. Redevelopment and Redesign of the Website

The statement of works for the contract specified the One Health website project as for site refresh and stabilisation, with additional contract work agreed for a tailored training package for the One Health EJP Communications Team and delivery of supportive documents. Specific tasks were carried under the following themes:

- Security
- Site refresh and stabilisation
- Search engine optimization (SEO) and analytics
- Search function
- Usability and appearance
- Layouts and designs
- Performance
- Training

To improve security, several actions were undertaken. 1) An overhaul of internal plugin software based on the site hardening configurations, as the implementation of a “quality” hardening tool acts to lock down further weaknesses specific to the content management system (CMS) to prevent opportunistic malicious activity. 2) Lockdown indexing and file leakage, for tracking and monitoring indexed content, available through [Google Search Console](#) (primary internet tracker) and modification of indexing configurations to ensure no sensitive, private data is being published through search. 3) Improved performance through tailored configuration and use of Cloudflare services. Cloudflare security has been activated and configured, tested, and improved over time to provide best balance of security and functionality. Cloudflare firewall is CMS agnostic and provides well-rounded protection. 4) Barclay Works provided supportive documentation to meet the GDPR guidelines and requirements, to assist the One Health EJP Communications Team in this aspect of data protection.

The following tasks were completed for the site refresh and stabilisation. 1) Improvement to the search function by creating a hierarchy for the [Uniform Resource Locators](#) (URLs). 2) The usability and appearance of the website was improved by delivering these features: a restyled, off-the-shelf theme

designed to incorporate OHEJP style guides; a responsive mobile functionality with use of adaptive layouts; consistent signposting, functionality and styling across the platform; clear 'Calls to action' made available; improved interactive maps (from a new plugin license purchase); commitment to accessibility through the [WCAG2 guidelines](#). 3) The stabilisation of the website was delivered by up-to-date web-stack following plugin overhaul and improved performance through tailored configuration and use of Cloudflare services for better Cloudflare integration with site and host; plugin updates and maintenance that pared back the use of plugins to reduce instability, to remove unnecessary code on site to improve maintainability in the future, with also the addition of new selected plugins, their integration, and updates. The stabilisation process also included reconfiguration and updates to the hosting setup that were made to bring the web stack up to a required level. This mainly pertains to [PHP version](#) 7.4.29. Work was done that improved backup size/speed and recovery time for the full site. To enhance performance, the site was made leaner through the removal of redundant/unnecessary plugins, content delivery network (CDN) deployed to reduce server load and domain name system (DNS) and protocol caching functionality.

Several tasks were completed related to SEO and analytics, as part of the site refresh, which included: 1) Configuration of Google Analytics and Google search appropriately with cross-application integration and [GA4 configuration](#). 2) Tag manager implementation for public and 'logged in' behavioural tracking across any events. 3) The ranking of connections and configurations for analytics and searches. 4) Tracking and fixing redirect and page errors during the redevelopment process.

Improving the search function of the website was done by implementation of a better search plugin that has improved the One Health EJP website search results and works across application plugins.

Improved usability and updating the appearance of the website was delivered, which involved: 1) The design of a restyled, off-the-shelf theme to incorporate One Health EJP style guides. 2) Responsive mobile functionality with use of adaptive layouts. 3) Consistent signposting, functionality, and styling across the platform that provided Clear 'Calls to action.' 4) Improved interactive maps on project pages. 4) Commitment to accessibility through the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.0 ([WCAG2](#)). 5) Rebuilding the menu to reduce options and provide content structure, which has created create URL depth and extend context across articles.

The website layouts and designs were restyled using either static or dynamic templates created for specific webpages and their content (e.g., Home page, Consortium page, Projects pages, Education and Training page, Short Term Missions pages, Latest News posts, Blog posts). For the dynamic templates this combined site search results output. Website performance was improved by configured caching and CDN parameters on-site and Cloudflare to deliver performance gains across the site for local and remote users.

Training on using the redesigned website was provided by Barclay Works using dynamic supportive documents made available online to One Health EJP Communications Team, which will also be shared with key [Med-Vet-Net Association](#) (MVNA) members managing the website in the long-term.

2. Accessing One Health EJP Resources on the Redesigned Website

The following key resources related to One Health EJP outputs and outcomes can be found on the redesigned website (Table 1).

Table 1: One Health EJP key resources (outputs and outcomes) available on the website.

Resource title	Further information	url link
One Health Outcome Inventory (OHOI)	A public database of scientific and integrative outcomes. It lists databases, strain collections, tools and other scientific outputs.	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/science-to-policy-translation/outcome-inventory
Project Impact Brochures	7 PDF brochures for METASTAVA, IMPART, TOX-Detect, LISTADAPT, FULL-FORCE, ARDIG & MATRIX projects. They share key messages, outputs and outcomes from each project in an easy-to-understand format.	https://onehealthjep.eu/projects/project-impact-brochures
OHEJP SimEx Project	SimEx reports, publications and tools used are listed on their webpage with links provided.	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/ohejp-simex-2022
Scientific Activities (report)	PDF document can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/OHEJP-Scientific-Activities_May2021.pdf
Collaboration for Success (overview brochure)	PDF document can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/OHEJP-Overview-Brochure_May2021.pdf
Strategic Research Agenda (report)	PDF document can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/One-Health-EJP-Strategic-Research-Agenda.pdf
Analysis of outcomes and uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders (brochure)	PDF document can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Analysis-of-outcomes-and-uptake-of-EJPs-outputs-by-stakeholders_Feb2023.pdf
Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (report)	PDF document can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/OHEJP-Strategic-Research-and-Innovation-Agenda_05.05.23.pdf
EU-JAMRAI Policy Briefs	10 Policy brief documents available to read and download.	https://onehealthjep.eu/about/stakeholders/addressing-amr-policy-briefs-from-eu-jamrai
Public Deliverables	The main deliverable documents for Work Packages 1 to 7 are listed, which can be accessed via Zenodo.	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/key-documents/public-deliverables
Publications	The publications from peer-reviewed journals produced by JIPs, JRPs, PhD projects, OHEJP SimEx and some Work	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/key-documents/publications

Resource title	Further information	url link
	Packages are listed from 2018 to 2023 with DOI links provided.	
Science to Policy Translation Reports	Thematic reports and Dissemination Workshop reports are listed, which can be accessed via Zenodo.	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/science-to-policy-translation/reports
Data Management Plans (DMPs)	A list of the final DMPs for each One Health EJP JIPs, JRPs, SimEx and WP4.	https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/science-to-policy-translation/data-management
Annual Reports from 2018 to 2022 (5 reports)	Each report has its own menu title. The 5 PDF documents can be read and downloaded from the website.	https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/One-Health-EJP-Annual-Report-2018.pdf https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Annual-Report-2019_100620.pdf https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/OHEJP-Annual-Report-2020_final-1.pdf https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/annual-reports/annual-report-2021 https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome/s/annual-reports/ohejp-annual-report-2022
WP6 Education and Training Bulletins	Monthly bulletins were produced from January to December 2021 and are listed on one webpage, with links to each one provided.	https://onehealthjep.eu/community/education-and-training/activities-bulletins
Consortium and External Newsletters	All newsletters from December 2018 to September 2023 are listed on one webpage, with links to individual newsletters provided.	https://onehealthjep.eu/community/news/newsletters
Latest News posts	All the latest news posts, from March 2020 to September 2023, can be accessed: when you click on the image it takes you to the individual news post.	https://onehealthjep.eu/community/news/latest-news
OHEJP Blog Posts	All the blog posts, from March 2019 to September 2023, can be accessed: when you click on the image it takes you to the individual blog post.	https://onehealthjep.eu/community/news/ohejp-blog
Communication Tools	OHEJP bespoke and branded Communication tools are available to download.	https://onehealthjep.eu/community/tools/communication-tools

The wide range of One Health EJP events and activities, which included Annual Scientific Meetings, various workshops (including ASM Satellite Workshops), Summer Schools, Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Modules and Short Term Missions, also have individual webpages accessible from the main website menu seen on the [homepage](#). The list of Annual Scientific Meetings (2018 to 2022) and Workshops are found under the main menu title “Outcomes”, whilst the list of Summer Schools (2019 to 2022), CPD modules (2020 to 2022) and Short Term Missions (2019-2022) are found under the main menu title “Community.” For each event, the webpage shares key information (e.g., conference agendas, case studies, reports etc.) and photos (where applicable).

3. Future Management of the Website

The One Health EJP website will be maintained by the MVNA when the programme finishes on 30th September 2023 and Barclay Works will be contracted by MVNA to provide professional services for this website. Handover of our website to this partner organisation ensures that all One Health EJP resources and information will continue to be digitally available to the One Health community for five years, with further updates managed by MVNA. The MVNA will be responsible for providing an umbrella website/portal for sustainable online One Health EJP outcomes (documents, databases, tools, etc.). New member registration for One Health EJP website was closed in March 2023 (once all JIPs and JRPs had finished) and the “Groups” area of the website was closed in September 2023 to facilitate website security and handover.